

RESULTS OF PERFORMING CORONARY ANGIOGRAPHY ON AN OUTPATIENT BASIS

Naimov Faridjon Fakhriddinovich

Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center

Interventional cardiologist in the angiography department

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Annotation: Indications and contraindications for performing CAG on an outpatient basis were determined, which in combination with the use of access of the forearm arteries made it possible to formulate an algorithm for safely performing CAG on an outpatient basis.

Keywords. functional classes, coronary heart disease, ECHO-KG

The problem of diagnosis and treatment of diseases of the cardiovascular system over the past decades remains one of the most urgent and priority tasks of world and domestic healthcare [14,16,18,20,22,25]. The most advanced and actively developing area of modern specialized and high-tech medical care (VTMP), especially for patients with various forms of coronary heart disease (CHD), is the X-ray endovascular method, characterized by high efficiency and low injury rate [13,15,17,19,21,23].

Despite the fact that the X-ray endovascular method often acts as a direct alternative to traditional surgical treatment, its spread was until recently limited by both a small number of vascular centers and the lack of modern X-ray endovascular installations in most medical institutions with cardiology departments and intensive care units, as well as an insufficient number of X-ray endovascular specialists. In recent years, there has been a distinct positive trend in the increase in the number of specialized clinics with X-ray endovascular diagnostics and treatment departments, which has led to a significant increase in the number of diagnostic and therapeutic interventions performed annually [2,4,6,8,10,12].

The existing foreign studies in this area differ in the criteria for inclusion and non-inclusion of patients, the peculiarities of patient management in the postoperative period, the absence of a single algorithm for selecting patients and different financial policies regarding the reduction of hospitalization [1,3,5,7,9,11,24].

The lack of experience of Uzbek centers for the study and implementation of such techniques, as well as the need to optimize existing approaches associated with long waiting times and hospitalization for diagnostic CAH and PCI, dictates the need to find adequate management schemes for patients with chronic coronary heart disease in medical institutions in Uzbekistan.

The purpose of the study. To determine the safety of diagnostic coronary angiography in outpatient settings, as well as the possibility of optimizing endovascular treatment of coronary arteries in patients with chronic coronary artery disease.

Material and methods: At the first stage of the study, in the period from March 2019 to December 2022, a total of 151 patients with chronic coronary heart disease or suspected of it were included in the study, who made up the main group, who underwent diagnostic CAH with discharge home a few hours after it was carried out. The comparison and control group consisted of a total of 83 patients with chronic coronary artery disease who underwent CAH in a hospital setting. During both diagnostic and therapeutic interventions, all patients were monitored in a Day Hospital (DS) with 6 beds. The DS was equipped in accordance with the equipment standard and additionally equipped with a centralized oxygen supply system, a central patient monitoring system for intensive observation units (ECG, blood pressure, arterial blood oxygen saturation), two defibrillators and a ventilator.

The average age of patients in the main group was 59.6±5.4 years, 68% of patients were men, 44% of patients suffered from arterial hypertension 1-2 ct, type 2 diabetes mellitus - 15%, dyslipidemia - 50.5% of patients. 5.3% of patients had a myocardial infarction less than 1 month old, 47.5% had a clinic of angina pectoris I - II functional classes (FC); III FC - in 8.7% of the patient. LVEF in all patients at the time of CAG in outpatient settings was higher than 35%.

The frequency of outpatient visits to a cardiologist in order to prepare for CAH in outpatient and inpatient settings averaged 2.5 ± 1.1 visits and 2.3± 1.3 visits (p=0.94). For hospitalization under the one-night program for the purpose of PCI and for hospitalization within the standard terms of PCI, the average number of visits to a cardiologist in the main group was 2.7 ± 1.2 visits and 2.1 ± 0.8 visits in the comparison group; there was no significant difference in the number of visits (p =0.87).

The laboratory examination included a biochemical blood test (12-16 parameters), a general blood test with a leukocyte formula and ESR, a general urine test, a blood test for infectious agents, a coagulogram, determination of blood type and Rh factor. The instrumental examination included an ECG in 12 leads with decoding, ECHO-KG, ultrasound of the arteries of the upper extremities, a stress test (stress ECHOCG), XM-ECG (if necessary), radiography of the heart with contrast of the esophagus.

As a result of the analysis, it was revealed that when performing CAG in outpatient settings, when compared with CAG in a 24-hour hospital (CS), the difference in direct medical expenses was 31.4% in favor of CAG in outpatient settings ($p < 0.0001$).

Despite the constant increase in the number of EVs on coronary arteries in Uzbekistan, as in most developed countries of Europe and the USA, the problem of optimizing the diagnosis and treatment of patients with coronary heart disease is one of the most acute. "Based on the need for examination and treatment of an increasing number of patients with coronary heart disease, new methods and schemes for managing patients before and after EV are being introduced into clinical practice, allowing to reduce the patient's stay in a specialized institution to 24 hours; with discharge after CAG after 2-4 hours of observation, and after PCI - the next morning. As it was shown in one of our recent published papers, this makes it possible to significantly increase the availability of various types of EV, reduce waiting lists and reduce material costs due to the reduction of bed days."

CONCLUSIONS.

1. Indications and contraindications for performing CAG on an outpatient basis were determined, which in combination with the use of access of the forearm arteries made it possible to formulate an algorithm for safely performing CAG on an outpatient basis.
2. Performing diagnostic CAH in patients with chronic coronary heart disease in outpatient settings is a safe method that reduces the duration of the patient's stay in the hospital to 3-4 hours. The safety of the approach is comparable to CAG performed in inpatient conditions, and is implemented by careful selection of patients at "low risk" of complications, taking into account the developed algorithm for their management before and after the procedure. When performing CAG in outpatient settings, a low incidence of complications was revealed: from the cardiovascular system - 0.5%, peripheral complications - 1.2%, comparable with the frequency of complications during CAG in inpatient conditions

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